

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF LONG FIBRES UNDULATIONS OCCURING DURING THE CURE OF A THERMOSETTING COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: An experimental device is presented for real time video records of long fibre undulation mechanism occurring during the cure of thermosetting systems. Video records allow fibre instability detection during the cure. Sensibility of heating rate and mass effect are analysed for T300 carbon fibre into an LY556 epoxy resin. Aims of the study are through real time waviness monitoring a better comprehension of undulation appearance and a quantitative data setup for fibre undulation description.

KEYWORDS: carbon fibre undulation, epoxy cure, video records, parametric study.

INTRODUCTION

Precise knowledge of material characteristics is getting more and more important for composite designs. Theoretical considerations about mechanical characteristics are not sufficient today for structure optimisation. This is especially the case for thermosets. Indeed, internal stresses are generated and several imperfections (bubbles, long fibres wavinesses...) are observed at the end of the process of cure, decreasing therefore theoretical mechanical performance of the obtained material. These phenomena are consistent in the manufacturing of thick composites. Presence of fibres regularly corrugated within the plies can be easily observed and this phenomenon also happens for thin composites made with long carbon fibres [1]. It was clearly observed that fibres are presented in an undulatory form at the end of cure. Volume shrinkage induced by the chemical reaction of cure for thermosets seems to be responsible for fibre destabilizing [2]. This author proposed a buckling mechanism generated by a compressive load apply onto long fibres, consequently to chemical shrinkage. Internal stresses generating these undulation defects result from the complex reaction of cure, mixing thermal, physicochemical, viscosity and mechanical phenomena by being thermoactivated and exothermal.

However, a lack of data exists in the literature about fibre undulations history. Available information only provides photography of the material after the cure [3], [4], [1], without any information on fibre instability appearance. Nevertheless [2] has studied this phenomenon and made the assumption that fibre undulations occurs during the gelation reaction. However, this assumption was not validated by the experiment since existing photographs only concern final observation after return at room temperature. Moreover effect of cure cycle on fibre waviness is unknown.

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Thus, aim of this study is focused on real time fibre waviness monitoring. Prior interest of video record is its ability to track fibre undulation history during the cure. An experimental device is proposed in order to provide answers to these questions by setting a basis of experimental data. Results and quantitative measurement of fibre wavelength and amplitude should allow a better understanding of fibre microbuckling instability and provide useful information for further modelling approaches.

POSITION OF THE PROBLEM

For better visibility reasons of fibre undulation mechanism observation, the choice of a single fibre specimen was done. Therefore in order to fix the problematic, a first cure of a single T300 carbon fibre plunged into an LY556 epoxy resin was done. Fig. 1 illustrates an example of fibre undulations observed after a heating at 5°C/min followed by an isothermal step of 30 min at 120°C.

Fig. 1: Undulated carbon T300 fibre within an LY556 epoxy matrix observed at room temperature

Since carbon fibre was initially straight inside of the resin, it is clearly established that undulations happen during the process of cure. In this way, real time video records of fibre undulation are necessary to grasp correlation between cure cycle and fibre waviness mechanism.

REAL TIME VIDEO RECORDS

Experimental device

Experimental device for real time video records consists of using a CCD digital camera connected to a 20 times magnification optical microscope to observe the heating of single fibre specimens. A Teflon mould placed under the microscope on an electrical heating table contains the T300/LY556 single fibre specimen to observe.

Temperature setup is essential for cure cycle correlations. Thus, temperature control is defined by heating rate control instead of an exact fixed temperature step. Indeed fibre undulations are assumed resulting from chemical shrinkage during the cure [2]. Therefore, variations of heating should induce variation of cure shrinkage and consequently affect fibre waviness phenomenon. So, isothermal step will be applied consequently to heating rate setup on electrical heating plate.

Protocol

Epoxy resin mixture consists of mixing a LY556 prepolymer in addition with an DY070 accelerator and a HY917 hardener (Ciba Geigy products). The Teflon mould is filled up to the half with the epoxy resin mixture. A 6 mm long T300 carbon fibre is placed freely on the surface of the resin. Little resin is then poured along the fibre to assure a total covering of it. However, resin viscosity decreases strongly during the heating and therefore induces fibre mobility. Thus, to avoid fibre exit of camera visual field, mould diameter was limited to 10 mm. Applied cure cycle is obtained by mould temperature measurement.

Video results

A T300 carbon fibre plunged into an LY556 epoxy resin was heated. Applied cure cycle is a 5°C/min ramp followed by an average step at 90°C.

Fibre undulation mechanism was detected and video record allows the reproduction of its history as shown by corresponding photographs on Fig 2.

Fig. 2: Video sequences of T300 fibre undulations appearance into an LY556 epoxy matrix

Fibre undulations are detected during the hot stage of the cure. This confirms previous works [2] since the phenomenon occurs quickly in around ten seconds. Undulations can be totally assimilated to a sinusoidal form and same results were obtained in presence of a Synolite 3720 II polyester resin.

Wavelength results and discussion

Fibre undulation wavelength is described by the apparent wavelength measurement. Results for T300/LY556 epoxy matrix are shown on Table 1.

Table 1: Apparent wavelength evolution during T300/LY556 single specimen cure

Relative time	Wavelength (μm)
t=0 second	Fibre still straight
t = 8 seconds	142
t = 24 seconds	105
t = 1 minute and 24 seconds	115
t = 3 minutes and 32 seconds	115
t = 15 minutes and 26 seconds (cooling down start)	115
at room temperature	125

Undulation mechanism happens quickly in comparison with cure time scale, less than ten seconds are enough. A first wavelength is observed around 140 microns and becomes stronger 16 seconds later since it reaches 105 microns. But one minute later waviness is generalised along the carbon fibre and stabilised around 115 microns up to the cooling down step. This unites with relaxation effects of fibre undulated stress applied onto the matrix according to its viscoelasticity. Moreover, it is interesting to note that fibre wavelength still increases during the cooling down step and tends to 125 microns at room temperature. This is a new relaxation effect of fibre undulation induced by the cooling. Indeed, during the cooling down, the fibre is subjected to thermal stresses produced by difference of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between fibre and matrix. Fibre dilates during cooling ($\text{CTE} = -0,74 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$) and matrix shrinks quite 200 times more ($\text{CTE}=150 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$). Elastic considerations are inadequate to explain fibre undulation relaxation. During the cooling the matrix is exposed to a glass transition from a rubbery state to a glassy state at room temperature. This transition owns real viscoelastic behaviour and previous work about this resin has shown that it could be described by a Zener modelling approach [2] with a relaxation time around 1 or 2 seconds. This may be enough to allow fibre thermal stresses to be relaxed within the matrix. This scenario seems to be reasonable because fibre cannot rotate so much to change its apparent wavelength measurement. This supposes a rotation of 23 degrees and is not compatible with matrix amorphous state.

Conclusion

Video records have established that fibre waviness phenomenon occurs during the hot stage of the cure. The mechanism happens suddenly in less than ten seconds for T300/LY556 system and relaxes partially due to viscoelastic properties of the matrix and glass transition during the cooling. Unfortunately, no amplitude measurement could be performed by video records because of inappropriate accuracy. However, fibre waviness mechanism was also recorded on other systems: coloured E glass fibres for better vision plunged into epoxy or polyester matrices, but quantitative exploitation are difficult because of bad vision quality. Thus, a reliable experimental protocol was established. It allows parametric studies of fibre undulations sensitivity to cure cycles.

PARAMETRIC STUDY PROTOCOL

This section presents a parametric study about the sensitivity of T300 carbon fibre undulation phenomenon to the cure of a LY556 thermosetting matrix. Therefore, aims of this study are :

- Sensitivity to heating rate
- Sensitivity to mass effects according to exothermal behaviour of thermosetting reaction. In addition to thermo activated aspect of the chemical reaction, shrinkage history suspected to be responsible for fibre waviness should be affected. Consequently fibre undulation should be dependent on mass effects.

Good field of view obtained on carbon fibres observations and their strategic use for high performance materials were preferred to glass fibres parametric study.

Experience plan and mould description

Two kinds of materials were tested: T300 carbon fibres plunged either into an LY556 epoxy matrix or a Synolite 3720 I1 polyester resin for 3 mm and 8 mm thick single fibre moulds. To make the same heating conditions onto Teflon moulds in order to grasp mass effects, same mould thickness were designed for 3 mm and 8 mm thick matrix, as shown on Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Teflon mould design for mass effect analysis

Temperature measurement

Two kinds of temperature were monitored during the cure: applied temperature loading during the heating and local temperature evolution in the fibre instability area. These temperature measurements are necessary to make:

- Correlation between fibre undulation and cure kinetics
- Correlation between fibre undulation and further cure shrinkage history determination
- Correlation between fibre undulation mechanism and any other physics involved during the cure

Note that local temperature measurement is done only in case of fibre waviness appearance.

This imply a special reproduction of the considered cure cycle applied to the resin mould, filled up with the same quantity of resin as previously in case of fibre waviness. A one mm thick thermocouple is then plunged into the resin free of carbon fibre, in the observed waviness area.

Degree of conversion determination

Correlation of fibre waviness phenomenon with cure kinetics requires local degree of conversion evolution. Local temperature history record is used for the cure kinetics determination. However, exact temperature profile observed is not simple to setup in a classical DSC analysis. Therefore, the way of cure kinetics simulation was chosen. Classical Gotro cure kinetics model as shown on Eqn. 1 was used.

Equation of cure kinetics solved is the one established for epoxy amine systems [5] as given by Eqn. 1.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K1 + K2 \alpha^m) \cdot (1-\alpha)^n \quad (1)$$

with : $K1 = a1 \exp(-e1/T)$ and $K2 = a2 \exp(-e2/T)$ where corresponding coefficients are given by table (2):

Table 2: Gotro cure kinetics coefficients for LY556 epoxy resin system

m	1,06	
n	1,79	
a1	$2,6 \cdot 10^{11}$	s^{-1}
a2	$1,19 \cdot 10^3$	s^{-1}
e1	$1,24 \cdot 10^4$	$^{\circ}K$
e2	$5,7 \cdot 10^3$	$^{\circ}K$

A finite difference scheme was used to solve Eqn. 1. Temperature input for the simulation is the temperature signal measured locally inside of the resin during its cure. This is reasonably representative for cure kinetics simulation since exothermal aspects are taken into account by resin local temperature input.

Real magnitude determination of fibre wavelength λ and amplitude A

Quantitative and useful description of fibre waviness characteristics require real magnitude measurement of fibre wavelength λ and amplitude A . Therefore, this section presents an experimental protocol developed for this purpose.

A 20 times optical magnification was enough to observe fibre wavelength. Observation of fibre waviness under two different directions with the free surface of the block of matrix containing the single carbon fibre allows waviness angular positioning and dimension. Principle of the method is explained on Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Real magnitude measurement principle of wavelength λ and amplitude A

χ denotes wavelength inclination angle with the top surface of the matrix block and λ_{real} is the real magnitude wavelength. Following equations solve these unknown factors of the problem:

$$\beta + \chi + \alpha = \pi/2, \text{ with } \sin(\beta) = \lambda_{measured}/\lambda_{real} \quad (1)$$

Then, for $\alpha = \alpha_1$, first angle of observation and for $\alpha = \alpha_2$ second angle, system to solve is:

$$\sin(\pi/2 - \alpha_1 - \chi) = \lambda_{1measured}/\lambda_{real} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and, } \sin(\pi/2 - \alpha_2 - \chi) = \lambda_{2measured}/\lambda_{real}$$

This leads to an analytical solution as given by Eqn. 3 and Eqn. 4 as:

$$\chi = -\alpha_1 - \arctan\left(\frac{-A_2 \text{ measured} + A_1 \text{ measured} \cos(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)}{A_1 \text{ measured} \sin(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{and, } \lambda_{real} = \lambda_{1 \text{ measured}} / \sin(\pi/2 - \alpha_1 - \chi) \quad (4)$$

The same technique was applied for real magnitude determination of fibre waviness amplitude.

Protocol accuracy discussion

Quality of real wavelength and amplitude quantitative measurements depends on apparent measurement accuracy. An example of apparent wavelength measured into two directions is shown on Table 3.

Table 3: Example of apparent wavelength measurement

	$\lambda_{\text{measured}}$ (μm)	$\chi_{\text{calculated}}$ ($^{\circ}$)	λ_{real} (μm)
$\alpha_1 = 0$	200	12,9	205
$\alpha_2 = 14^{\circ}$	183		

Apparent wavelength measurement is obtained by pixel counting technique provided by Adobe Photoshop software. Thus, maximal uncertainty is estimated being less than 5%. Consequences of 5% uncertainty on real wavelength determination are exposed on Table 4.

Table 4: 5% apparent wavelength uncertainty consequences

$\chi_{\text{calculated}}$ ($^{\circ}$)	λ_{real} (μm)
22,2	227

Thus, best accuracy of real magnitude measurement cannot be less than 11% for wavelength determination. This is acceptable as a first step whereas wavelength inclination angle is changing up to 72% since it is strongly dependant on observation angles and measured amplitude as indicated by Eqn. 3. Observation angles must be much more different than those used to improve the accuracy of the device. A solution is for example better optical systems with greater field view depth. Anyway, interests are in the fact that the proposed protocol provides a simple methodology for real measurement of fibre undulations.

RESULTS

Local temperature evolution

Exothermal behaviours and mass effects are observed by local temperature monitoring during the cure of LY556 epoxy resin and a Synolite 3720 II polyester resin. Thermal disturb induced by thermocouple measurement technique is assumed being negligible according to the one mm thin thermocouple probe plunged into the resin. Results are shown on Fig. 5 for epoxy resin cures and clearly illustrate existence of exothermal effects.

Fig. 5: Epoxy resin local temperature monitoring during cure and mass effects

Exothermal peak increases with resin thickness and demonstrates mass effects onto exothermal behaviour. Moreover exothermal depends strongly on applied cure cycle as shown on Fig. 5 by same mould results.

It is then obvious that cure cycle and mass effects induce strong thermal gradients. Thermosetting reaction will be affected by these parameters since they generate degree of conversion gradients and therefore gradients of chemical shrinkage. This is important information that must be taken into account for internal stress growth comprehension.

Fibre undulation appearance

Video records have allowed detection of fibre undulation appearance versus cure cycle. Time of undulation detection was superposed on local temperature evolution records.

Results are shown on Fig. 6 and Fig. 7.

Fig. 6: 8 mm thick epoxy resin local temperature monitoring during cure and fibre undulation detection (4.8°C/min ramp up to 138°C)

Fig. 7: 8 mm thick epoxy resin local temperature monitoring during cure and fibre undulation detection (5°C/min ramp up to 144°C)

Fibre instability appearance is detected closed to the exothermal peak, for a quite high level of degree of cure. This indication confirms that microbuckling instability approaches [5] can be

developed since instability appears for a solid state of the matrix, but quite away from gelation reaction. Dependency of fibre waviness real magnitude characteristics to heating rate is presented in next section.

Fibre undulation sensitivity to heating rate

Effects of heating rate are presented on Fig 8 and Fig 9 for epoxy and polyester resins. Fibre wavelength and amplitude are real magnitude measurements. Heating rates were obtained by local temperature records.

Fig. 8: 8 mm thick polyester resin heating rate effect on T300 carbon fibre undulation

Fig. 9: 8 mm thick epoxy resin heating rate effect on T300 carbon fibre undulation

Wavelength decreases with heating rate increase. This is in good correspondence with the scenario of chemical shrinkage responsibility for fibre undulations. Indeed, it seems logical to accept that, according to thermo activated behaviour of thermosetting resins, chemical reaction is acting stronger with a strong or a fast heating. Corresponding shrinkage should therefore reach higher level and thus apply higher level of undulation onto the fibre. This scenario is verified with a fibre wavelength into an epoxy matrix greater than into a polyester matrix, a logical consequence of polyester chemical shrinkage well known as being usually greater than epoxy shrinkage. However, amplitude is also decreasing with heating rate

increasing. This is certainly related to the viscous behaviour of the resin that allows relaxation effects on fibre undulations.

Fibre waviness observations provide therefore a good description of matrix cure state and furthermore a too strong local heating rate may definitely generate fibre failure as shown on Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: Example of local carbon T300 fibre failure observed during the heating of an epoxy resin

CONCLUSION

A simple and reproducible protocol has been developed for real time observations of fibre undulations appearance and growth. Fibre undulation happens quickly during the hot stage of the cure and was observed for carbon fibre either into an epoxy matrix or a polyester resin. Quantitative information about undulation wavelength and amplitude were obtained and their dependencies to cure cycle have been established. Thus, undulation history records, viscous behaviour certainly responsible for relaxation effects and undulation mechanism dependency to thermal history are novel results that must be taken into account for further modelling approaches. Fibre instability results from chemical shrinkage, rigidity evolution, thermal history and resin load transfer onto the fibre. Single fibre undulation analysis is an excellent indicator for cure quality and a fine testing structure for further chemical thermal and mechanical models of the cure.

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